

Integrated Child Development Programme in Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Early childhood is a crucial period for a child's overall development, laying the foundation for social, cognitive, physical, emotional and psychological growth. The nation should prioritize children's development, not just because they are weak, but because they are crucial assets and future human resources. India is overpopulated, has high infant mortality rates, and is impoverished and malnourished. To address the health and mortality challenges affecting the country, a significant number of health professionals are needed. The Anganwadi system is a village-level child care and maternal development project sponsored by the Indian Government, which started in October 1975. It aims to improve affordable and accessible healthcare facilities by utilizing the local population. Basic health services provided under the Anganwadi system include counselling, provision of contraception, education, nutritional supplements, and preschool activities. These services are offered by individuals known as Anganwadi Workers. The system is an integral part of the Indian healthcare system. Ongoing efforts are made to provide accessible and affordable healthcare to the community through the Anganwadi system. This includes assessing malnutrition among children and women in Uttarakhand and monitoring the growth and progress of ICDS in the region, including budget allocation and expenditure.

Keywords: ICDS, AWWs, AWCs, Malnutrition, National Family Health Survey

Introduction

Children play a crucial role in human development as the foundation for lifelong learning and growth is established during these formative years. It is widely recognised that the economic development of any country relies on investing in human resource development. India faces challenges such as overpopulation, malnutrition, poverty, and high infant mortality rates. Addressing these health and mortality issues requires a significant number of healthcare professionals. The Anganwadi system aims to improve access to affordable healthcare by leveraging the local population.

Anganwadi is a type of child and maternal care centre in India, part of the ICDS program sponsored by the central government. The ICDS scheme was launched on October 2, 1975, as a

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flagship program for children and lactating mothers. The Anganwadi offers basic health services including counselling, contraception provision, education, nutritional supplements, and pre-school activities. Anganwadi Workers deliver these services as part of the Indian healthcare system.

The ICDS scheme is designed for children up to 6 years old, as well as pregnant and lactating mothers, and women between 16 and 44 years of age. Strengthening the target community's education, nutrition, and overall health is the scheme's main objective.

The main objectives of the scheme are:

1. To enhance children 0-6 years old health and nutritional condition.
2. To build a foundation for a child's psychological, social and physical growth.
3. To lower the incidence of disease, mortality, hunger and school dropout.
4. To effectively coordinate the policies and implementations across departments to promote children's development.
5. To enhance the mother's capacity to supply her child with the essential medical and nutritional requirements through a nutritious diet.

Review of Literature

Jitendra B. Surwade *et.al* (2013)

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Latur district to assess the utilization of the ICDS scheme in Urban and Rural areas. 500 children were selected 250 each from urban and rural. 254 children for the rural block and 252 children for the urban block were enrolled. The study found that 48.03% of children from urban areas and 37.7% of children from rural areas had utilized supplementary nutrition. In Urban areas, 57.72% of children had utilized non-formal preschool education whereas in rural areas it was 53.79%. Utilization of health check-up facilities was 25% in rural areas whereas in urban areas it was 21.65%. Utilization of immunization services in urban and rural areas was 90.95% and 94.44%. In urban areas, 46.46% of children were malnourished whereas in rural areas 55.56% of children were malnourished.

K- Helena *et.al* (2014)

To evaluate the state of services for children who are beneficiaries of the ICDS program, a cross-sectional study was carried out in three ICDS blocks within the Greater Visakhapatnam Municipal Corporation between November 2010 and October 2012. A total sample of 360 children from 45 Anganwadi centres were studied. The study found that most were aged between 25 to 36 months. 99.2%, 93.6% and 92% were immunized and received pre-school education and supplementary nutrition respectively. 15% of children received benefits from the AWWs' treatment of mild illnesses, whereas 59.7% of children's growth was tracked. Stunted and underweight children comprised 47.2% and 25.3% respectively. The study recommended the need to focus on growth monitoring, home visits and nutrition counselling that leads to promoting child health.

Silva *et.al* (2015)

The study centred on the dietary status of children going to Anganwadi in a rural region of Goa under the ICDS program. To find out the predominance of lack of health sustenance, involving stunting, wasting and underweight, in children between the ages of six months to six years, a cross-sectional study was conducted from January to June 2015. The study revealed that 33.4% of children were underweight, 24% were encountering wasting, and 31.5% were stunted. Furthermore, 9.2% of children were severely underweight, 10.4% were severely wasted, and 8.7% were severely stunted. Children aged 6-36 months were found more underweight (38.1%) than the children in the age group of 37-72 months (24.9%) and it was also found more in the lower class which was 51.3% as compared to the upper class which was 17% respectively. The study recommended the need for continuous monitoring of AWCs.

U.Vinod Kumar Andey *et.al* (2019)

A cross-sectional study was carried out as part of the Mangalagiri rural ICDS project to ascertain the sociodemographic profile and level of knowledge among AWWs. For the study, 212 AWWs in total were interviewed. According to the study, 63.7% (135) of AWWs had more than ten years of work experience, and roughly 58% (123) of AWWs had only completed their sixth through tenth grade. The majority of AWWs (96.7%) knew the most about vaccinations, followed by referral services (93.4%), growth monitoring (62.5%), health check-ups (75.1%), nutrition, and health education (70%). Only 75% of AWWs knew less about supplemental nutrition, the workload, and excessive record keeping.

Objective of the Study

1. To study year-wise budgetary allocation and expenditure under the ICDS Scheme in Uttarakhand.
2. To study the year-wise progress of the ICDS Scheme in Uttarakhand.
3. To study the Malnutrition level among children and women in Uttarakhand.

Research Methodology

The data used in the present study are secondary. The Department of Women Empowerment and Child Development, Government of Uttarakhand, provided information on budget allocation and expenditure, participants in ICDS programs and the number of undernourished and severely undernourished children. Data regarding Operated Anganwadi Centres in Uttarakhand was available on the official website of the government of Uttarakhand, and the data regarding undernutrition among children and women was available in the National Family Health Survey of Uttarakhand.

In Uttarakhand, Child Development Schemes were operated in three development blocks (Chakrata, Kirtinagar, and Dehradun) during 1978-79. Currently, there are 97 rural projects, and 8 urban projects, totalling 105 child development projects operating in 95 development blocks across all 13 districts of the state.

Table :1 Number of Operated Anganwadi Centres in Uttarakhand

Years	Number of Anganwadi Centres operated under Child Development projects
2011-12	17828
2012-13	18801
2013-14	19329
2014-15	19430
2015-16	19506
2016-17	14708
2017-18	19898
2018-19	19997
2019-20	20067
2020-21	20046
2021-22	20067

Source : Statistical Dairy of Uttarakhand

The table above indicates the number of operated Anganwadi centres in the state. In 2011-12, the number of operated Anganwadi Centres was 17828, which increased to 20067 in 2021-22. From the table, it is evident that the number of Anganwadi centres has increased over the years.

Table: 2 Budget Allocation and Expenditure under ICDS

(Rs. in Crores)

Years	Budget Provision	Budget Sanction	Expenditure	% Change in Expenditure
2011-12	348.87	229.74	187.41	-
2012-13	347.25	189.43	157.82	-15.78%
2013-14	479.67	479.67	303.48	92.30%
2014-15	849.20	823.08	519.04	71.02%
2015-16	802.38	682.74	430.29	-17.09%
2016-17	662.55	657.50	460.56	7.03%
2017-18	718.07	674.34	420.25	-8.75%
2018-19	827.34	783.31	558.56	32.91%
2019-20	946.87	856.12	680.52	21.83%
2020-21	1025.38	698.81	605.22	-11.06%
2021-22	1205.38	1035.60	736.68	21.72%
2022-23	1755.06	1127.26	925.26	25.59%

Source : Department of Women Empowerment & Child Development Government of Uttarakhand

The table shows that the budget allocation and expenditures for ICDS have increased over the years. In 2011-12, the budget provision for ICDS was 348.87 crores. Out of this amount, 229.74 crores were sanctioned, and the total expenditure was 187.41 crores. In contrast, for 2022-23, the budget provision increased to 1755.06 crores, with 1127.26 crores being sanctioned and total expenditure amounting to 925.26 crores.

The expenditure decreased by 15.78% from 2011-12 to 2012-13, but then it increased by 92.30% in 2013-14 and by 71.02% in 2014-15. In 2015-16, the expenditure decreased by 17.09% and then increased by 7.03% in 2016-17. In 2017-18, there was an 8.75% decrease, followed by increases of 32.91% and 21.83% in 2018-19 and 2019-20. Expenditure decreased by 11.06% in 2020-21 and then increased by 25.59% up to 2022-23.

Table: 3 Number of Beneficiaries from Financial Year 2011-12 to 2022-23

Years	Pregnant Women	06 months to 3 Years Children	3 years to 6 Years Children	Adolescent Girls
2011-12	152884	313033	228219	105709
2012-13	2006	3077	225005	189
2013-14	162111	384694	243515	17970
2014-15	162684	407535	224567	185998
2015-16	181738	467231	217490	175576
2016-17	179248	465063	198144	214390
2017-18	166466	424731	179100	191462
2018-19	174673	465063	179100	168471
2019-20	174260	437155	169677	173993
2020-21	182138	444940	165538	238925
2021-22	156725	392264	213527	152010
2022-23	103169	263657	131238	140798

Source : Department of Women Empowerment & Child Development Government of Uttarakhand

The table above shows the number of beneficiaries from the year 2011-12 to 2022-23. In 2011-12, the ICDS scheme benefited the following numbers of individuals: 152884 pregnant women, 313003 children aged 6 months to 3 years, 228219 children aged 3 years to 6 years, and 105709 adolescent girls. In 2022-23, the beneficiaries numbered: 103169 pregnant women, 263657 children aged 6 months to 3 years, 131238 children aged 3 years to 6 years, and 140798 adolescent girls.

Table: 4 Malnourished and Severely Malnourished Children from years 2011-12 to 2022-23

Years	Malnourished	% change in malnourished	Severely Malnourished	% change in severely malnourished
2011-12	85698	-	3562	-
2012-13	92543	7.98%	7546	111.85%
2013-14	62453	-32.51%	4722	-37.42%
2014-15	47993	-23.15%	4094	-13.30%
2015-16	32492	-32.30%	2870	-29.90%
2016-17	25149	-22.60%	1686	-41.25%
2017-18	16305	-35.17%	1153	-31.61%
2018-19	15765	-3.31%	1454	26.11%
2019-20	11409	-27.63%	1370	-5.78%
2020-21	8856	-22.38%	1129	-17.59%
2021-22	7665	-13.45%	1117	-1.06%
2022-23	5556	-27.51%	800	-28.38%

Source : Department of Women Empowerment & Child Development Government of Uttarakhand

The table shows the number of malnourished and severely malnourished children in the state. From 2011–12 to 2012–13, the percentage of malnourished children increased by 7.98%; by 2022–2023—it decreased by 27.51%. The percentage of severely malnourished children increased by 111.85% from 2011-2012 to 2012-13 but has been consistently decreasing by 28.38% in the following years until 2022-23.

Table 5: National Family Health Survey of Uttarakhand

	NFHS-4(2015-16)	NFHS-5 (2019-21)
Stunted children under the age of five	33.5%	27%
Wasted Children under the age of five	19.5%	13.3%
Severely wasted children under the age of five	9%	4.7%
Underweight children under the age of five	26.6%	21%
Children with anaemia aged 6-59 months	59.8%	58.8%
Anaemic pregnant women between the ages of 15 and 49	46.5%	46.4%
All anaemic women between the ages of 15 and 49	45.2%	42.6%

Source : National Family Health Survey Report 2015-16 and 2019-21

The NFHS reports for the years 2015–16 and 2019–21 show that the prevalence of stunting decreased from 33.5% to 27%, wasting decreased from 19.5% to 13.3%, severe wasting decreased from 9% to 4.7%, and underweight prevalence decreased from 26.6% to 21% among children.

The percentage of children aged 6-59 months who were anaemic dropped from 59.8% to 58.8%, while pregnant women aged 15-49 showed no improvement in their anaemia rates. But the percentage of women aged 15 to 49 who were anaemic fell from 45.2% to 42.6%.

Conclusion

From the above study, the following findings are stated.

1. Across all 13 state districts, 105 child development projects run in 95 development blocks, comprising 8 urban and 97 rural projects. The number of Anganwadi centres has increased from the year 2011-12 to 2021-22. In 2011-12, there were 17828 Anganwadi centres, while in 2021-22, the number has increased to 20067.
2. Expenditure under the ICDS scheme in respect of Anganwadi services has increased from 187.41 crore in 2011-12 to 925.26 crore in 2022-23. The expenditures are mainly for the construction of AWCS, providing drinking water and sanitation, supplementary nutrition, and all other basic amenities needed under Anganwadi services. Over the years, the number of beneficiaries has also increased.
3. Eliminating malnutrition is one of the most critical global challenges and is also essential for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. The level of nutrition in India has dropped to alarming levels, yet our country still has the largest number of stunted and wasted children in the world.

4. The NFHS of Uttarakhand from 2015–16 to 2020–21 reports that the number of malnourished and severely malnourished children in the state decreased from 2011–12 to 2022-23. Although stunting, underweight, and malnutrition have become less common in children over time, the rate of anaemia in both women and children has not decreased.

Recommendation

Though Uttarakhand has made strides in implementing the ICDS, including more Anganwadi centres, more children receiving supplemental nutrition and attending pre-educational schools, as well as expenditure under the ICDS, there still exists a significant issue of undernutrition and anaemia among children and women. Government agencies should adopt a comprehensive, coordinated, multi-sectoral approach that considers the diverse challenges at the local level, and there is a need for better governance.

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